

Acknowledgement

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Chemical Constituents of *Eucalyptus citriodora* Roots

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EUCALYPTUS *citriodora* (F : Myrtaceae) is distributed¹ in India, Australia and many other countries. An essential oil (0.5-2.0%) is obtained from its leaves which is used in soap perfumery and as a source of citronellal. *Eucalyptus*² is used in the treatment of catarrhal states of bronchopulmonary mucous membrane, intermittent and septic fevers, diphtheria, whooping cough etc. Earlier examination showed the presence of oil and flavonoids in the leaves³⁻⁶ while the gum⁷ contained ellagic acid and flavonoids.

The present note deals with the chemical examination of the roots of *Eucalyptus citriodora*. The roots (3 kg) were extracted with hot acetone and alcohol separately. The acetone extract, on column chromatography over silica gel, gave six compounds (A-F). Compound A (β -sitosterol) crystallised from chloroform-methanol as colourless needles (50 mg), m.p. 136°, $[\alpha]_D - 34.5^\circ$ (CHCl_3). Co-TLC and m.m.p. with an authentic sample confirmed its identity⁸. Compound B (Betulinic acid) crystallised from methanol as silky needles (500 mg), m.p. 312-14°, $[\alpha]_D + 9^\circ$ (CHCl_3). It responded to L.B. test and formed an acetate, m.p. 286-88°. Identity established by m.m.p. with an authentic sample of betulinic acid⁹, co-tlc and superimposable ir.

Compound C (ursolic acid) crystallised from methanol as colourless needles (200 mg), m.p.

288-90°, $[\alpha]_D + 69^\circ$ (CHCl_3) and gave +ive L. B. test (pink $\rightarrow$ blue). Acetate, m.p. 245-46°, $[\alpha]_D + 57^\circ$ (CHCl_3). It was identified as ursolic acid¹⁰ by m.m.p., co-tlc and superimposable ir.

Compound D (7-O-methylaromadendrin) crystallised from CHCl_3 -MeOH as light pale flat needles (2.0 g), m.p. 187-88°, $[\alpha]_D + 30^\circ$ (MeOH) and gave a transient purple to brown colour with FeCl_3 and +ive Zn/HCl test. Acetate, m.p. 136-37° ($\text{M}^+ 428$). It resembled in all respect with authentic 7-O-methylaromadendrin⁷ (ir, uv, nmr and mass). Compound E (aromadendrin) crystallised from methanol-benzene as colourless needles (800 mg), m.p. 247-48°, $[\alpha]_D + 25.5^\circ$ (MeOH) ($\text{M}^+ 288$). Acetate, m.p. 80-82°. It was characterised as aromadendrin⁷ by ir, uv, nmr, mass and by direct comparison with an authentic sample (co-tlc, m.m.p.). Compound F (fustin) obtained as colourless solid from ethyl acetate-petroleum ether (250 mg), m.p. 213-15°, gave green colour with FeCl_3 and +ive Zn/HCl test. Acetate, m.p. 149-51°. It was identified as fustin¹¹ by ir, uv, nmr and by direct comparison with an authentic sample (co-tlc and m.m.p.).

Thus the occurrence of β -sitosterol, betulinic acid, ursolic acid, aromadendrin and 7-O-methylaromadendrin is noted for the first time in the roots of a *Eucalyptus* species and fustin for the first time in *Eucalyptus*.

No single compound could be isolated from alcohol extract.

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